

Risk factors linked with elderly, truck and office worker drivers: A literature review in light of automated driving

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Abstract

This study tries to identify and review risk factors that impact road safety and driving performance focusing more on three types of users, namely elderly drivers, truck operators, and office workers. The present review is part of research conducted within the EU H2020 HADRIAN project, which aims at developing an innovative Human Machine Interface (HMI) that will provide seamless “fluid” interactions between the driver and the automated vehicle. The literature review was conducted using popular databases such as Google Scholar, Science Direct, and Scopus using specific search terms and prioritization criteria for studies coming mainly from Europe and the U.S, and after 2005. Then, the reviewed risk factors were discussed based on how they can be extended and adapted at the different future AD levels and what risk factors should be considered in future safety analysis depending on the AD level. The aforementioned review will be exploited by the HADRIAN project, like any other HMI stakeholder, in order to develop a human-centered assessment methodology that will evaluate the way the human interacts with potential HMI configurations. Finally, the reviewed risk factors could guide stakeholders in accomplishing a safer transition from manual to autonomous driving for all road users.

Keywords: Elderly drivers, Truck drivers, Working drivers, Risk factor, Driving performance, Road safety

1. Introduction

Road traffic fatalities and injuries are a serious threat to public health as they are the 8th leading cause of death worldwide with approximately 1.3 million deaths per year and many more (20-50 million) suffer non-fatal injuries [1]. Despite the fact that the death rate (deaths per population) presents a declining trend, still, every year about 18 fatalities per 100.000 population are recorded which is quite concerning [2]. Focusing on the cost of road accidents, in 2015-values of 31 European countries, the estimation of preventing a fatality varies from 0.7 to 3.0 million Euro [3].

For many decades, the research spotlight has shed light on many risk factors which contribute to accidents. A relative analysis of Thomas et al., 2013 [4] investigated road accident data from 6 countries and found that 72% of the examined accidents involve factors related to human factor, indicating that human factor is a major concern on road safety. In this direction, relevant studies estimated that human factor is responsible for 94% of road accidents [5]. The remainder is due to factors related to a combination of the road environment and vehicle factors [6].

At the same time, when intelligent transportation systems will become widely available in future societies, aspects such as human factors, congestion, and energy efficiency will be improved [7]. Hence, it can be assumed that by the evolution of automated driving; the human factor can be reduced or get assisted during AD and this will result in the reduction of road fatalities. Another hypothesis indicates that if the driving task could be shifted to optimal (assuming error-free systems for automated driving), collision risk should be reduced or to an extent eliminated by removing human factor [8]. Nevertheless, a more realistic assumption is that human error will be replaced by crashes caused by imperfect automated systems in the intermediary stages i.e., in “mixed traffic” conditions [9]. To that end, the Forum of European Road Safety Research Institutes (FERSI) developed the main principles for “safety through automation”. A key principle for automation safety is the necessity for “Human-Centred Design”, in which all possible user profiles should be considered when designing Autonomous Vehicles (AVs). Also, “Human-Centred Design” includes safe communication through road users, and safe interactions with vulnerable road users [9], indicating the key role of human factor during designing AVs.

This review aims to identify risk factors that impact road safety and driving performance focusing more on three types of users, namely elderly drivers, truck operators, and office workers (i.e., working and driving simultaneously; feasible at higher levels of automation). In Subsection 2.1, the importance of investigating the risk factors of these use cases is unfolded in terms of road safety. Additionally, this review attempts to highlight the reviewed risk factors that should be considered in the future safety analysis of automated driving (AD) applications. Then, the reviewed risk factors were

discussed on how they can be extended and adapted at the different AD levels and what risk factors should be considered in future safety analysis in regards to the AD level.

The paper is structured as follows: after the introductory section with a brief presentation of the importance of this review in combination with AD development, a section follows with the examined use case description and the literature review methodology. After that, the literature findings are presented and analyzed, along with different subsections for the three main use cases. Then the discussion follows and the reviewed factors are discussed in relation to the different AD levels and then the limitations, and future research are given. Finally, the conclusions follow with the significant outcomes of this study, and then the acknowledgments follow.

2. Methodology

2.1 Examined Use Cases

In this subsection, the use cases used for the current review are described. The use case drivers or the user types considered were inspired by research conducted within the EU H2020 HADRIAN project, which aims at developing an innovative Human Machine Interface (HMI) that will provide seamless interaction (named “fluid”) between the driver and the automated vehicle. Simultaneously, the importance and purpose of choosing these three specific use cases are explained.

Over the last decades, life expectancy is increased and it is estimated to continue having an upward trend in the coming decades [10] and combining the fact that the population is ageing, it comes as a logical consequence that the proportion of elderly drivers increases [11]. Nowadays, the elderly population consists of 18% of the whole European population. This percentage will be increased steadily in the future as a worldwide report indicates due to the reduction in the fertility level [12], the declined birth rates, the baby-boom generation (which consists a significant proportion of the population) is ageing, and the increased longevity of humans. Due to these explanations, it is estimated that 24% and 28% of the population will be aged ≥ 65 years in 2030 and 2050, respectively [13]. As a result, the definition of classification among elderly drivers is required for this study. Elderly drivers are considered as the age group of 65 years old and over according to [14, 15]. Sometimes it can be separated into two subcategories namely; the young elderly (65-74 years) and the older elderly (85 years and older) [16, 17].

In the context of elderly drivers and road safety, it is worth investigating the impact of the third age on accidents and road safety in general. Several published studies show a significantly higher crash involvement rate is observed regarding older drivers compared to the younger group [18–20]. Furthermore, analyzing the fatal accidents appears that the fatality crash rate is higher for the older drivers compared to other age groups [21, 22]. At the same time, a study shows that injury severity is strongly related to age, thus an older driver is more likely to be involved in an injury or fatal road accident compared to a younger one, probably because of the declining physical condition [23]. Taking these aspects into consideration, the risk factors of elderly drivers are critical to be analyzed as they are more vulnerable to trauma and likely to have a collision and especially for future applications which will give the opportunity to elderly users the ability to commute [24].

Concerning the truck drivers, the total traffic fleet consists of a notable proportion of trucks (around 10%) [25] and presents different features in comparison to passenger cars. For instance, truck drivers cover longer distances as they use their trucks for commercial purposes. A thorough investigation of the associated risk factors is required as truck drivers were responsible for 16% of the accidents [26]. Also, a study supplements the aforementioned statement by highlighting the different safety patterns among different-weighted types of vehicles by stating that “the lighter the vehicle, the less risk to other road users, and the heavier the vehicle, the less risk to its occupants” [27], consequently, trucks may be more dangerous for other vehicles, motorbikes, and vulnerable road users, than for the drivers themselves.

With regards to office worker drivers (i.e., working and driving simultaneously), this use case attempts to approach a future mobility need. Through higher levels of automation, these drivers will possibly be engaged in non-driving-related tasks (NDRT) i.e. laptops, vehicle displays, smartphones, or even sleeping. In the existing literature, this specific use case has not been adequately analyzed yet, since it is impossible to work during driving nowadays. Therefore, this type of driver should be analyzed and further investigated in terms of potential risk factors.

2.2 Literature review methodology

The literature search was conducted on the leading databases with published studies and most of them are published in scientific journals after peer-review process. These scientific databases were Scopus, Science Direct, and Google Scholar using specific search terms and prioritization criteria for studies coming mainly from Europe and the U.S, and after 2005. Also, all findings of SafetyCube DSS [28] were exploited. In general, Table 1, describes the used search terms for the review. The first column includes the basic search terms and the second column demonstrates additional keywords depending on the corresponding topic.

The first step of the literature review methodology was the search in the aforementioned databases, as mentioned before. The second step was to screen the title and the abstract, and judge if it was suitable. The third step concerned the results,

which were sought to be statistically significant along with a rational and reasonable methodology. In total, 300 papers were screened and about 90 studies were included in this review.

Tab 1: Search terms of the literature review

Basic search terms	Additional search terms
“accident probability”	“mental workload”, “inattention”, “mind wandering”, “distraction”, “reaction time”, “response time”, “fatigue”, “sleepiness”, “drowsiness”, “cognitive functions”, “cognitive abilities”, “driving performance”, “headway”, “speed”, “turning head”, “neck flexibility”, “vision”, “night time”, “medical conditions”, “hearing”, “diseases”, “medication”, “drugs”, “emotions”, “stress”, “anger”, “spatial perception”, “impairments”, “driving experience”, “mental workload”, “sleep disorders”, “Mind-wandering”, “night time driving”, “speeding”, “drivers' age”, “reaction time”, “age”, “weather conditions”, “adverse weather”, “driving experience”, “stress”, “anger”, “boredom”, “perception”, “traffic density”, “traffic flow”, “cognitive functions”, “cognitive abilities”, “road type”, “sex”, “joint” “alcohol”, “drugs”, “vision”, “spatial perception”, “risk taking”, “medical”, “obesity”, “emotions”, “speed choice”, “medication”
“road safety”	
“risk factor” or “risk”	
“elderly”	
“older”	
“aging” or “ageing” or “aged”	
“truck”	
“heavy duty”	
“heavy vehicle”	
“trailer”	
“worker”	
“working”	
“workaholic”	
“driver”	
“drive”	

3. Analysis and Results

3.1 Risk Factors

In this section, the obtained findings are presented, and, specifically, risk factors for each use case as identified based on the literature. The identified factors were distinguished for each examined use case; namely elderly, truck, and office worker drivers. As mentioned before, these use cases were inspired by research conducted within the EU H2020 HADRIAN project. The literature review found several risk factors that significantly impact safety and driving performance and are analyzed in the following subsections. In Table 2, the factors are presented in three columns. Each column represents each examined use case or type of driver.

Also, as can be seen in Table 2, the obtained factors were categorized into categories per use case. The factors were categorized with regards to elderly drivers into three main categories namely; age-related impairments, age-related medical conditions, and age-related medication. The implemented categorization follows the structure of a European Commission’s report ElderSafe [13] and a published review [15] (i.e., age-related functional limitations, illnesses, and medication). Besides, risk factors regarding truck drivers are separated into the following categories: i) Driver-related Factors, ii) Work-related Conditions, iii) Driving Conditions. Furthermore, office worker drivers factors are incorporated in the category of Working-related Conditions. The categorization was implemented in a sense that the reviewed factors to be categorized into as few as possible dedicated categories, as well as taking into account the three fundamental elements of driving task: human - traffic environment – vehicle.

Tab. 2: Factors that impact on safety and driving performance

1. Elderly Drivers	2. Truck Drivers	3. Office Worker Drivers
<u>1.1 Age-related Impairments:</u>	<u>2.1 Driver-related Factors:</u>	<u>3.1 Working-related Conditions:</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental Workload • Inattention • Distraction • Reaction Time • Fatigue • Cognitive Functions • Headway & Speed • Joint Flexibility • Vision & Hearing • Emotions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Driving Experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distraction • Inattention • Stress • Fatigue
<u>1.2 Age-related Medical Conditions</u>	<u>2.2 Work-related Conditions:</u>	

1. Elderly Drivers	2. Truck Drivers	3. Office Worker Drivers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatigue • Working Hours • Sleep Duration • Sleep Disorders • Nighttime Driving • Obesity • Distraction • Inattention • Vehicle Configuration • Company's Safety Policy 	
<u>1.3 Age-Related Medication</u>	<u>2.3 Driving Conditions:</u>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road Type 	

3.2 Elderly Drivers

3.2.1 Age-related Impairments

In this section, all possible age-related impairments of elderly drivers are analyzed and therefore aspects related to road safety research are presented. Before going deeper into the risk factors, it is worth mentioning that in the majority of the reviewed studies there is not a clear relation between age-related impairments and accident risk. The only occasions that this relation becomes evident are under the following severe impairments: severe sensory, perceptual or cognitive limitations, and severe illnesses (Brouwer & Davidse, 2002 as cited in [13]). Nevertheless, the rest of the included factors are considered to impact driving performance and probably to an extent the accident risk.

Mental Workload: The workload can be defined as the concept of "resources" or "residual resources" [29]. The study of Isabelle and Simon, 2020 [30] reveals that elderly drivers compared to the younger age group differed significantly regarding the load that was devoted to mental demand and physical demand. In the same context, the mental workload of the elderly was higher compared to the younger drivers and this outcome became worse in more complex driving situations such as overtaking maneuvers [31]. Another study indicated that elderly drivers had a higher mental workload due to the fact that in the experiment they did not perceive a higher percentage of "missed signals" [32]. The aforementioned findings can be combined with the fact that there is a close relationship between the variables of mental workload of the aged drivers and driving performance [33]. Therefore, it can be concluded the perceived workload is different between elderly and younger drivers which leads to a different impact on their driving performance.

Inattention: Inattention can be defined as "daydreaming and distraction through the state of mind (pondering, etc.) in a certain way induces a level of distraction to the person driving" [34]. Research findings presented that a higher frequency of self-reported inattention state was highly correlated with higher risk during driving [35]. Nevertheless, a study by Qu et al., 2015 [35] explains that probably the reason that older drivers reported less mind-wandering was the declined processing capabilities.

Distraction: Drivers' distraction occurs when a sudden event induces an attentional shift away from the driving task. Research showed that in-vehicle tasks, namely hands-free mobile phone conversation and interaction with entertainment/information system, decreased several variables concerning driving performance and these results were quite stable for all different driver age groups and environmental difficulties [36]. Older drivers tended to engage selectively in distraction tasks according to driving difficulty, for example, they engaged less (with their distractive activity) when driving becomes more challenging in comparison with less challenging maneuvers [37].

Reaction Time: The average reaction time to sudden events of the older drivers was significantly higher than younger age groups [20]. Another research showed that reaction time increased gradually with age [38], the same influence, also, found in between older ages 70 to 89 years old [39]. Mental workload increased further the average reaction time to sudden events and regarding elderly drivers a more remarkable influence was observed [14, 40]. The response to critical events became more inaccurate as the task difficulty increased, hence older experiment participants made more errors than other age groups. Consequently, they had a significantly higher no-response rate to unexpected events compared to other age groups [14]

Fatigue: The definition of fatigue varies greatly in the literature with terms such as 'fatigue', 'sleepiness', and 'drowsiness' being used interchangeably [41]. The Oxford dictionary definition of fatigue can be explained as "extreme tiredness resulting from mental or physical exertion or illness" [42]. The literature review showed that the elderly have a higher probability to cause a fatigue-related crash than other age groups [43], while older drivers perceived themselves as more fatigued while driving compared to younger groups [44].

Cognitive Functions: There is a great concern about "age-related cognitive decline" that impacts cognitive functions among the elderly population. Specifically, the study of Salthouse et al., 2003 [45] showed that cognitive abilities and cognitive performance such as measures of speed processing declined in the older population. The elderly needed more

time to process complex information before an accurate response [14]. Another study concluded that mental flexibility is worse for the elderly [30]. These findings can be combined with the finding that the declined cognitive abilities were found to be significantly correlated with driving performance [46, 47]. On the contrary, the study of Song et al., 2017 [48] extracted that older age groups have the same cognitive measurements as the younger ones, however, drivers above 58 years old were used which contradicts the age limit of 65 years for elderly drivers, as stated at the section explaining the use cases.

Headway & Speed: The headway time is defined as the elapsed time between the front of the lead vehicle passing a point on the roadway and the front of the following vehicle passing the same point [49] and headway distance as the elapsed distance respectively. According to some studies [20, 30, 50], elderly drivers have developed an adaptive and defensive strategy by keeping longer headways [46, 51] and lower speeds [20, 30]. However, mixed results have been found with regards to speed deviations. Some researchers found that the older age group deviated in speed less compared to the younger age groups [20, 48] while [46, 51] found higher deviations. With regards to the headway variation, the age group of elderly drivers deviated more than the rest [51].

Joint Flexibility: Another research finding is neck flexibility measurement, which showed a significant effect on driving performance. More specifically, elderly drivers show less neck flexibility measurement [52]. Aged drivers tended to make moderately sharper or tighter turns than younger drivers due to the reduced head and neck flexibility, and subsequently, they lacked checking traffic vehicles [53].

Vision & Hearing: Elderly drivers have a significantly decreased performance in peripheral motion contrast threshold and age was found to be strongly correlated with peripheral motion contrast threshold. Furthermore, the peripheral motion indicator was remarkably associated with crashes and driving performance [54]. Another finding was that there was a significant reduction in the elderly's visual field size in dynamic conditions [30]. From the results of the experiment from [52], older drivers looked more at lane markings on the road in order to have a correct lane position, however younger drivers looked more at dynamic objects-threats such as the traffic vehicles. Furthermore, older drivers tended to look less often on the road for potential threats [55]. According to Bao & Boyle [56], they tended to look less at their available scanning range such as the left, right, rearview mirror or somewhere random compared to the middle-aged. On specific occasions, the elderly looked and scanned significantly less left and right when they passed through an intersection. Moreover, they checked the rearview mirror significantly less compared to the middle-aged.

In the context of vision impairments, visual deficiencies are associated with crash involvement [57]. Moreover, another study implies that impaired visual processing and glaucoma may play a role that older driver crashes and to by extent result in injuries [58]. With regards to the declining vision, a number of papers indicated that reduced vision and visual acuity impacted negatively on accident involvement (for both injury and non-injury accidents) [57, 58]. These results showed that poor vision, which is more probable for elderlies, impacted statistically significant on accident involvement. On the other hand, a study by Gresset & Meyer [59] presented a neutral effect of the vision-related variables on accidents.

Simultaneously, focusing on hearing loss, a study by Picard et al. [60] indicated that there was a modest but significant correlation and association between hearing loss and crash involvement. Besides, Green et al., 2013 and Ivers et al., 1999 [57, 61] found a non-significant increase and unclear effect on accidents, respectively. In addition to the association between hearing loss and crash involvement, a recent study by Dultz et al. [62] found that hearing impairment can be associated with higher injury severity. Focusing on hearing loss, a study by Picard et al. [60] indicated that there was a modest but significant correlation and association between hearing loss and crash involvement. Besides, Green et al., 2013 and Ivers et al., 1999 [57, 61] found a non-significant increase and unclear effect on accidents, respectively. In addition to the association between hearing loss and crash involvement, a recent study by Dultz et al. [62] found that hearing impairment can be associated with higher injury severity.

Emotions: Some studies found that older drivers tended to drive less aggressively compared to the younger age groups [63, 64] and as a consequence, elderlies were less risky on the road.

3.2.2 Age-related Medical Conditions

Amongst elderly people, there is a higher probability to be diagnosed with one or more specific medical conditions which are more dominant in the older adult population [13]. A study by Clarke et al., 2010 [43] found older drivers with chronic or acute illness, in general, can contribute to more crashes. Medical conditions can potentially impact the accident risk of elderly road users [65] and it is not the condition itself that increased the risk, but the influence of the condition on the functional abilities and skills of elderly drivers to respond appropriately to critical events [66]. Similarly, the observed increased risk can be caused by the medications which are being prescribed [67]. According to two meta-analyses of Charlton et al., 2010 and Vaa, 2003 [65, 67], the identified age-related medical conditions which are presented to be associated with higher accident risk are *Alcohol abuse, Cardiovascular diseases, Cerebrovascular diseases, Depression, Dementia, Multiple Sclerosis, Diabetes mellitus, Epilepsy, Hearing impairments, Musculoskeletal and motor disability conditions, Parkinson's disease, Psychiatric disorders, Renal disease, Schizophrenia, Sleep apnoea, Vision impairments, Hearing impairments, Heart disease or stroke, Cataracts, Mental disorders, Neurological disease, and Arthritis/*

Locomotor disability [13, 68]. Furthermore, having more than one illness which is defined as “comorbidity” is more common among the elderly population and is considered also associated with a higher crash risk [13].

3.2.3 Age-Related Medication

With regards to medications amongst the elderly, these are highly associated with the risk of accidents [68]. More specifically, Vaa, 2003 [67] estimated the accident risk of medical influence and it was found to be equal to 1.58 and at a 95% confidence interval ranging from 1.45 to 1.73. Meaning that drivers who are being prescribed medication presented a 58% increase in accident risk compared to non-medical road users.

3.3 Truck Drivers

The main two characteristics that differentiate truck drivers from private car drivers are i) devoting a great amount of their day driving, and covering longer distances [69] ii) the type of vehicle.

3.3.1 Driver-related Factors

Age & Driving Experience: According to Duke et al., 2010 and Helinä and Summala, 2001 [26, 70], a significant predictor of being principally responsible for an accident was age. Another research by Maycock [71] found that the accident frequency was highest for the youngest group of 17–29 years and the accident frequency decreased to less than one-third of this for drivers over 55 years of age; this result was considered to be combined effects of both age and driving experience. In combination with the literature finding on the general population of young commuters (i.e., non-commercial drivers), young drivers are more prone to get involved in accidents than other ages [72, 73].

3.3.2 Work-related Conditions

Fatigue, Working Hours, Sleep Duration, Sleep Disorders, Nighttime Driving, Obesity: When truck drivers drive for six or more hours, studies have found that they are more prone to get involved in crashes than colleagues with fewer hours [74]. Furthermore, another finding is that 4% of the drivers had reported being tired prior to crashes [75]. Another study investigated the causes of fatigue and are namely; driving the day, duration of wakefulness, inadequate sleep, sleep disorders, and prolonged work hours [76]. Also, obesity is considered to be a fatigue-related accident factor for truck drivers according to [77].

Distraction/ Inattention: The study of Hanowski et al., 2005 [78] analyzed critical naturalistic incidents with long-haul truck drivers and the results showed that the frequency and duration of a task were found to contribute to critical incidents occurrence. Also, it was clear that visually demanding tasks have the highest degree of risk compared to other types of driving-related tasks.

Vehicle Configuration: Double trailer vehicles showed involvement in accidents that increased steadily as the number of driving hours increased [74]. In this context, double trailer driving had an injury risk ratio of 1.32 compared to the single-trailer configuration [79]

Company's Safety Policy: In addition, another study indicated that the safety policy of a truck company was a significant countermeasure for fatigue-inducing factors associated with driving a heavy vehicle [80]. It was also found that the safety performance of certified carriers was significantly better after certification [81].

3.3.3 Driving Conditions

Road Type: Urban areas were found to have higher traffic densities, and at the same time lower operating speeds and lower speeds and as a result contribute to a lower probability of injury or death given an accident with truck drivers [75].

3.4 Office Worker Drivers

Existing literature has not investigated the futuristic mobility need of a working driver since it is impossible to work while driving with current automation levels. However, this is expected to be a future mobility need since the higher levels of automation make it feasible for the drivers to interact with non-driving-related tasks (NDRT). Hence, the included factors for office workers were derived mainly from assumptions depending on their special needs.

3.4.1 Working-related Conditions

Distraction & Inattention: Especially, at the intermediate SAE automation levels (i.e., SAE levels 2, 3) prior to the highly automated, the driving task will still require human inputs and interventions such as Take Over Request (TOR) maneuvers. However, the drivers could be more probable to be distracted and inattentive during the TORs. This is due to the fact that AD will give the ability to the drivers to be involved with NDRTs and since they are office workers; they could

probably be busy with office-based liabilities. Therefore, the drivers would look at their laptop, smartphone, or tablet and think about their open topics and liabilities. Naujoks et al. [82] classified various NDRTs concerning their impact on driver performance in takeover scenarios and concludes that this is a fundamental contribution toward the creation of safe AD functions. Research showed that in-vehicle tasks during manual driving; hands-free mobile phone conversation and interaction with entertainment/information system, decreased several variables concerning driving performance and these results were quite stable for all different driver age groups and environmental difficulties [36, 83]. Another study modeled the reaction time and the results showed that reaction time was increased during the distraction tasks [84]. Consequently, taking into account the increased reaction time due to the distraction, accident probability is likely to be increased.

Stress: Emotion of stress probably will be a risk factor for office workers as they will be worried about their open topics and liabilities. Probably, at intermediate AD levels, office worker drivers will experience more stress which will be external to driving tasks and this requires further research. Based on the existing literature, emotions, in general, significantly impact driving performance and accident probability were impatience, aggressiveness, boredom, and stress [85–88].

Fatigue: Fatigue or drowsiness, as stated and analyzed previously, will be more probable for office workers to be more fatigued than other commuters as they will have to return home after a working day. Fatigued driving after a long working day may increase the accident risk of all drivers or even fall asleep. With regards to TORs, fatigued drivers could cause a serious hazard in take-over situations where situation awareness is required [89].

4. Discussion

This work performed a review of risk factors that impact road safety and driving performance of three types of users, namely elderly drivers, truck operators, and office workers in the era of automated driving.

At the intermediate SAE automation levels (i.e., SAE levels 2, 3) prior to the highly automated (i.e., SAE levels 4, 5), the driving task will still require human inputs and interventions [24]. At these two AD levels, apart from the TORs, there will be sections within the commuting routes that AD will not be available and the drivers will be required to drive manually. Therefore, within these manual driving parts, the reviewed risk factors will be present and AV manufacturers could focus on eliminating or mitigating these. Significant effort should also be concentrated on elderly drivers since AD will be more attractive to them. TORs will be a major part of AD tasks and should be investigated more profoundly in terms of risk factors and their impact on accident risk and driving performance. Special focus and further investigation should be implemented for the following risk factors during TORs regardless of the use cases:

- **Distraction:** the drivers will be more probable to be distracted and inattentive during the TORs. This is due to the fact that AVs would permit the driver to be distracted with NDRTs when AD is enabled. Hence, the drivers would look at their laptop, smartphone, or tablet prior to TORs and not outside the driving environment [82].
- **Stress:** Emotion of stress probably will be a risk factor for all use cases since will experience stress which will be external from driving tasks and this requires further research. Based on the existing literature, emotions, in general, significantly impact driving performance and accident probability.
- **Fatigue:** The driver could be fatigued or even fall asleep during AD. The users could fall asleep more easily since they will be not engaged with the driving task. As stated previously, fatigue can be a major concern for the drivers' safety as it can predict more road accidents.
- **Driving Experience:** Driving experience will be a determinant factor for the whole performance of the TOR maneuver, especially in urgent requests. Also, driving experience is correlated with the ability of the driver to check all necessary information in the driving environment before taking over control and have adequate reaction times.

At SAE levels 4 and 5, however, there will be no human interventions and hence the obtained risk factors associated with the user might not exist. Currently, human factor is responsible for the majority of accidents and an ideal hypothesis for AD would be that by removing human from the task of driving, the elimination of accident risk will be accomplished [8, 90]. Though, a more realistic assumption is that human error will be replaced by accidents caused by imperfect automated systems [9]. Therefore, another type of analysis would be needed when these levels will become widely available.

Nevertheless, this study is not without shortcomings, and therefore, future research could focus on covering the remaining gaps that this work did not cover. A more detailed connection between risk factors and AD can be developed and analyzed as there is no existing work in this direction. In addition, a notable limitation, which was mentioned at the beginning of this paper, is that there is not a direct connection between risk factors and accident probability because it is almost impossible to investigate if these specific risk factors are directly correlated with the recorded accident data. Nevertheless, in this review, it was assumed based on literature that many risk factors affect driving behaviour and performance and consequently the risk probability.

5. Conclusions

This study tried to identify and review risk factors that impact road safety and driving performance focusing more on three types of users, namely elderly drivers, truck operators, and office workers (i.e., working and driving simultaneously; feasible at higher levels of automation). This review attempted to highlight the reviewed risk factors that should be considered in future safety analyses. Then, the reviewed risk factors were discussed on how they can be extended and adapted at the different future AD levels and what risk factors should be considered into future safety analysis with regards to the AD level. Overall, a lack of direct correlation between risk factors with accident risk or reported road accidents can be observed.

The aforementioned review will be exploited by the HADRIAN project, in order to develop a human-centered assessment methodology that will evaluate the way the human interacts with potential HMI configurations. Finally, the reviewed risk factors could guide stakeholders in accomplishing a safer transition to autonomous and manual driving for all road users.

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